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ABSTRACTS

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Identification of AMR markers associated with Mutations via computational tools

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Abstract: Recent years, exploitation and misapplication of antibiotics has given rise to a phenomenon called AMR viz. Antimicrobial resistance has become a major global threat of this century, leading to high morbidity and mortality rates. Various pathogens involved in AMR such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* or *Escherichia coli* evolve with high rates of resistance towards antibiotics, this has become a challenge to find an accurate solution. Therefore, identification of mechanisms through which resistance occurs and detection of these genes called ARGs are the major processes for understanding AMR. A bioinformatics approach to AMR has an advantage, as its time effective, large data analysis gives a clear idea for clinical research. The aim of the study is to focus on identification of molecular markers coding for AMR. A pipeline designed to procure molecular markers through computational tools was developed.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, *staphylococcus aureus*, molecular markers, SNPs, mutation, ARG.

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